

THE ROLE OF JOB SATISFACTION IN MEDIATING THE EFFECT OF WORKLOAD AND COMPETENCE ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE AT PT PLN (PERSERO) UP2B NTB

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to analyze the effect of workload and competence on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediating variable at PT PLN (Persero) UP2B NTB. The research method used was quantitative with a census approach, involving the entire employee population of 54 people. Data were collected through a Likert scale questionnaire and analyzed using *Structural Equation Modeling - Partial Least Square* (SEM-PLS) with the help of *SmartPLS software*. The results of the study showed that: (1) workload did not have a significant effect on employee performance; (2) competence had a positive and significant effect on employee performance; (3) workload did not have a significant effect on job satisfaction; (4) competence had a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction; (5) job satisfaction had a positive and significant effect on employee performance; (6) job satisfaction did not mediate the relationship between workload and employee performance; (7) job satisfaction partially mediated the relationship between competence and employee performance. The *R-square value* for job satisfaction was 72.5% and employee performance was 84.1%, with a *Goodness of Fit value* of 0.770 (high category).

Keywords: workload, competence, job satisfaction, employee performance

INTRODUCTION

Rapid technological developments and digitalization have required organizations, both public and private, to continuously adapt and implement strategic changes to achieve their stated goals. In this context, human resource (HR) management is a key determinant of organizational success. Of all available resources, HR is the only asset possessing reason, emotion, skills, knowledge, and creative and innovative power (Mangkunegara, 2017; Afandi, 2018). Proper HR management will drive improved performance, foster work discipline, foster harmonious working relationships, and foster employee career development. Employee performance, defined as the quality and quantity of work performed in carrying out assigned tasks, is the primary measure of organizational success (Mangkunegara, 2017; Fahmi, 2017). Employee performance is influenced by various internal and external factors, including workload, competence, and job satisfaction (Gibson et al., 2013; Robbins & Judge, 2009). Excessive workload can lead to stress, fatigue, and decreased productivity, while too little workload can lead to boredom and a lack of motivation (Joesyiana et al., 2022; Santihari et al., 2025; Wang Chaohui et al., 2020). Competence, which encompasses knowledge, skills, and work attitudes, is also a key determinant of employee effectiveness in carrying out their duties (Wibowo, 2016; Sedarmayanti, 2017). Employees with high competence tend to be more confident, capable of solving problems, and producing superior performance. Meanwhile, job satisfaction—a person's positive feelings about their job—has been widely shown to contribute to improved performance, loyalty, and work morale (Toyo, 2021; Rahmi et al., 2025).

However, various previous studies have shown inconsistent results regarding the influence of workload and competence on performance, as well as the mediating role of job satisfaction. For example, studies by Joesyiana et al. (2022) and Wijaya & Suarmanayasa (2025) found that high workloads decrease employee performance, while Utomo et al. (2024) reported a positive effect of workload on performance. Similarly, competence was reported to have a positive

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and significant effect by Krisnawati & Bagia (2021) and Pratama et al. (2023), but not a significant effect in studies by Khatimah et al. (2020) and Suzanna et al. (2023). Job satisfaction also shows inconsistencies: Wirya et al. (2020), Herawati et al. (2022), and Wahyudi et al. (2023) found a positive effect on performance, while Fauziek & Yanuar (2021) and Widya Nastiti (2022) reported no effect. This inconsistency indicates the existence of contextual factors, such as organizational characteristics, work culture, and research methodology that need to be explored further (Nurhandayani, 2024; Abdurrahman et al., 2025). This research was conducted at PT PLN (Persero) Load Regulatory Implementation Unit (UP2B) West Nusa Tenggara (NTB), a technical implementation unit responsible for regulating and controlling the electricity system in NTB Province. Based on initial observations, the performance of UP2B NTB employees in the last three semesters (semester I 2024 – semester I 2025) has not reached the company's target of 110%. The highest performance realization only reached 106.02% (semester I 2025), still with a gap of around 3.98%. In addition, employees face a wide work area (Lombok and Sumbawa Islands) with a limited number of positions (54 people), resulting in an unbalanced workload. Only 22% of employees have competency certifications appropriate to their field of work, while 56% have inappropriate certifications and 22% are not yet certified. This condition is suspected to affect employee performance. Although several studies have examined the relationship between workload, competence, and job satisfaction on performance, few have specifically examined the mediating role of job satisfaction in the context of a technical and real-time electricity organization such as the UP2B. Research by Afrizal et al. (2021) at the Aceh National Land Agency (BPN) found that competence and workload significantly influence performance through job satisfaction. Similarly, Budiyanto et al. (2024) at the Semarang Madya Dua Tax Office (KPP Madya Dua) showed that competence positively influences performance through job satisfaction, while workload has no direct effect. Setyono & Safaria (2025) at PT PNM ULaMM reported that workload does not directly influence performance but does influence it through job satisfaction. However, these results may not necessarily apply to the PLN UP2B NTB environment, which is characterized by high time-pressured work, strict standard operating procedures (SOPs), and systemic responsibility for regional electricity reliability. Therefore, this research is important to fill this *gap*.

The novelty of this research lies in: (1) the unique research object, namely the electrical system load regulator implementation unit which was just established in November 2023, so it has HR dynamics that are still in the maturation stage; (2) testing the mediating role of job satisfaction on the relationship between workload and competence on performance simultaneously in one model; (3) the use of the SEM-PLS method which is able to handle small samples (54 respondents) and test complex relationships between variables. This research is expected to provide theoretical contributions to the development of HR management science, especially the *Job Demands-Resources theory* (Bakker & Demerouti, 2014) which states that *job demands* (workload) and *job resources* (competence, support) interact to influence performance through employee well-being (job satisfaction). Practically, the research results can be used as consideration for the management of PLN UP2B NTB in formulating workload management policies, increasing competence, and creating job satisfaction to optimize employee performance. Based on this background, the problem formulation in this study is: (1) Does workload affect employee performance? (2) Does competence affect employee performance? (3) Does workload affect job satisfaction? (4) Does competence affect job satisfaction? (5) Does job satisfaction affect employee performance? (6) Does job satisfaction mediate the relationship between workload and employee performance? (7) Does job satisfaction mediate the relationship between competence and employee performance? The purpose of this study is to analyze these influences and test the mediating role of job satisfaction in the PT PLN (Persero) UP2B NTB environment.

METHOD

This study uses a quantitative approach with a causality design that aims to examine the influence between variables and the mediating role. The study was conducted at PT PLN (Persero) Load Regulatory Implementation Unit (UP2B) West Nusa Tenggara (NTB) from February to May 2026. The study population was all 54 permanent employees of UP2B NTB. Given the relatively small population, a census technique was used so that the entire population was used as a research sample (Sugiyono, 2017). The research variables consist of two exogenous variables, namely workload (X1) and competence (X2), one endogenous variable, namely employee performance (Y), and one mediating variable, namely job satisfaction (M). The operational definition of each variable refers to proven theories. Workload is measured by indicators of work conditions, use of working time, targets achieved, and work standards (Robbins, 2001; Ahmad et al., 2019). Competence is measured through three dimensions: knowledge, skills, and abilities (Sedarmayanti, 2017). Job satisfaction is measured by indicators of the work itself, compensation, promotion opportunities, supervision, and

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coworkers (Afandi, 2018). Employee performance is measured based on quality, quantity, timeliness, effectiveness, and independence (Robbins, 2001). The research instrument was a questionnaire with a Likert scale of 1–5 (strongly disagree to strongly agree). Prior to use, the questionnaire was tested for validity and reliability on 30 initial respondents. The test results showed all items were valid (*loading factor values* > 0.60) and reliable (*Cronbach's alpha values* > 0.90). Data were collected through in-person questionnaire distribution and through *Google Forms* Data analysis was performed using *Structural Equation Modeling* (SEM) based on *Partial Least Square* (PLS) with the help of SmartPLS software version 4.0. The selection of PLS-SEM was based on its ability to handle small samples (<100) and does not require the assumption of multivariate normal distribution (Hair et al., 2017; Ghazali, 2016). Model evaluation was carried out in two stages: (1) evaluation of the measurement model (*outer model*) which includes convergent validity tests ($AVE > 0.5$ and *loading factor* > 0.6), *discriminant validity* (*cross loading value*), and reliability (*composite reliability* > 0.7); (2) evaluation of the structural model (*inner model*) which includes R-square tests, *effect size* (f^2), *predictive relevance* (Q^2), *goodness of fit* (GoF), and hypothesis testing through a *bootstrapping procedure* with 5,000 subsamples to produce t-statistics and p-values. The mediation effect was tested using *the Variance Accounted For* (VAF) approach (Hair et al., 2017).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study involved 54 employees of PT PLN (Persero) UP2B NTB, consisting of various divisions: finance and general affairs, K3 and security, procurement executors, operational facilities, system operations 1 (Lombok), and system operations 2 (Sumbawa). Respondent characteristics showed a male predominance (94.4%), productive age 26–30 years (46.3%), and 6–10 years of service (46.3%). Respondents' educational backgrounds were quite diverse, with the proportion of high school/vocational school and bachelor's degrees each at 38.9%, and only 7.4% had postgraduate education. Certification data showed that only 22% of employees had competency certificates relevant to their current field of work, 56% had certificates but were not relevant, and 22% did not have certification. This condition reflects the challenges of human resource development in the unit, which was only established in November 2023.

Descriptively, respondents' perceptions of the four research variables were in the high category (perception scores 73.64%–78.66%). Employee performance scored highest on the quality indicator (82.96%) and lowest on quantity (59.26% on item Y4). Workload was rated highest on job standards (78.52%), while superior competencies were rated highest on skills (78.89%) and abilities (80.74%). Job satisfaction showed very high scores on supervision (82.22%) and coworkers (82.59%). This description provides a basis for suggesting that although the company's 110% target has not been achieved, employee perceptions of their performance are relatively good. Before testing the hypothesis, the model was evaluated through *the outer model* and *inner model*. The results of *convergent validity* showed that all indicators had a *loading factor* > 0.7 after eliminating M3 (0.581) and Y4 (0.010). The AVE value of each variable: workload (0.837), competence (0.749), job satisfaction (0.807), employee performance (0.674) — all > 0.5 (Hair et al., 2017). The *discriminant validity test* through *cross-loading* proved that each indicator had the highest correlation with its own construct compared to other constructs. Reliability was guaranteed with *composite reliability* > 0.90 and *Cronbach's alpha* > 0.90 for all constructs.

The structural model (*inner model*) shows an *R-square value* for job satisfaction of 0.725, meaning 72.5% of the variation in job satisfaction is explained by workload and competence together (moderate category approaching strong). The *R-square value* for employee performance is 0.841 (strong category), meaning 84.1% of the variation in performance is explained by workload, competence, and job satisfaction. The almost identical *adjusted R-square values* (0.714 and 0.831) indicate a stable model without predictor inflation. The *effect size* (f^2) of competence on job satisfaction is 0.478 (large effect), on performance is 0.203 (moderate effect); while workload has an $f^2 < 0.025$ (very small effect). The *predictive relevance* (Q^2) value for job satisfaction (0.672) and performance (0.772) > 0, indicating the model has strong predictive ability. *Goodness of Fit* (GoF) of 0.770 > 0.38 (large criteria), confirms that the model is very suitable to the empirical data.

1) The Effect of Workload on Employee Performance

Statistical results: Path coefficient = 0.136; standard deviation = 0.173; t-statistic = 0.787 (< 1.96); p-value = 0.216 (> 0.05). Hypothesis H1 which states that workload has a negative effect on employee performance is rejected. These findings indicate that statistically, workload does not significantly contribute to the improvement or decline in employee performance at PT PLN UP2B NTB. Although the coefficient value is positive (0.136), this insignificance indicates that the observed relationship may be due to sampling chance, rather than a real effect in the population. A theoretical

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explanation can be found in the *Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Theory* (Bakker & Demerouti, 2014). This theory states that *job demands* (including workload, time pressure, task complexity) do not always negatively impact performance if they are balanced with adequate *job resources* (competence, social support, autonomy, and feedback). In the context of UP2B NTB, work is *real-time*, structured, and standardized through strict SOPs and clear job descriptions. Every employee understands the workload expectations they will face from the start of their placement (based on the Decree). Therefore, workload fluctuations (rising and decreasing task volumes) are not perceived as extraordinary or threatening, but rather as a normal part of daily operational dynamics. Furthermore, PT PLN UP2B NTB has a work culture characterized by high professionalism and systemic responsibility. Employees in the load management unit recognize that any delay or error in regulating the electricity system can have a broad impact on the people of NTB Province. This awareness creates a strong internal commitment, ensuring consistent performance regardless of the workload. In other words, workload is no longer a sensitive variable for performance because it has been internalized as a routine job requirement. These findings align with several previous studies. Farismawarni & Sumbogo (2023), in a study of physical work environments, reported that workload had no significant effect on employee performance, as employees had good adaptability. Ina Handariani et al. (2023) also found that workload had no effect on performance among teachers, which was explained by the habit of facing high workloads and sudden training. Al Marshoudi et al. (2023) added that high workloads do not always reduce performance as long as the organization is able to create a supportive work environment and maintain employee well-being. The consistency of these findings indicates that in organizations with mature SOPs and a strong work culture, workload loses its predictive power on performance.

2) The Influence of Competence on Employee Performance

Statistical results: Path coefficient = 0.472; standard deviation = 0.229; t-statistic = 2.058 (> 1.96); p-value = 0.020 (< 0.05). Hypothesis H2 is accepted (significant positive effect).

Competence has been shown to be a key predictor of employee performance. A coefficient of 0.472 indicates that every one standard deviation increase in competency will increase performance by 0.472 standard deviations, with other variables controlled. This finding is highly relevant to the highly technical and complex nature of work at the NTB UP2B. As a unit responsible for managing the electrical system load on two large islands (Lombok and Sumbawa), employees are required to master SCADA (*Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition*) systems, transmission network management, system protection, and the ability to make quick decisions during disruptions. Without adequate competency, even a small error can result in a regional power outage.

Competence in this study was measured through three dimensions: knowledge, skills, and abilities. Descriptive results show that the skills and abilities dimensions scored the highest (78.89% and 80.74%), indicating that UP2B NTB employees generally have good practical skills. However, only 22% of employees have certification in their respective fields, so there is still significant room for improvement. The positive influence of competence on performance can be explained through the following mechanisms: (1) highly competent employees are better able to plan and organize work; (2) they adapt more quickly to technological changes (e.g., SCADA system updates); (3) they are more confident in taking initiative and taking responsibility. These results are consistent with various studies. Jayadiputra et al. (2024) found that competence had a positive and significant effect on performance among personnel managers in Buleleng Regency, even being the strongest factor compared to motivation and leadership style. Irmayanti et al. (2020) also reported that improving competence through education and training directly impacted performance among employees. Darmawan et al. (2023) among village officials throughout Buleleng Regency reinforced these findings. In the context of an electricity company, Mantrawan et al. (2024) at PT PLN UPT Bali showed that competence is an important determinant of job satisfaction and performance. Therefore, investment in competence development (technical training, certification, *workshops*, *mentoring*) should be a strategic priority for UP2B NTB management to drive performance towards the 110% target.

3) The Effect of Workload on Job Satisfaction

Statistical results: Path coefficient = 0.076; standard deviation = 0.273; t-statistic = 0.277 (< 1.96); p-value = 0.391 (> 0.05). Hypothesis H3 is rejected (no significant effect). Although high workloads are often intuitively associated with dissatisfaction, this study found no statistical evidence to support this relationship. The very small positive coefficient (0.076) and large standard deviation (0.273) indicate that the estimates are unstable and unreliable. This means that high or low workloads do not significantly contribute to feelings of satisfaction or dissatisfaction among NTB UP2B employees. A key explanation lies in the meaning of workload in the eyes of employees. In an operational environment loaded with strategic responsibilities (maintaining electricity reliability), a high workload is often interpreted as a sign of

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organizational confidence in their abilities. Employees feel valued for being entrusted with critical tasks. This transforms workload from a source of stress to a source of professional pride. Furthermore, scheduled shift work, task rotation, and support from coworkers and superiors (as reflected in supervisor satisfaction scores of 82.22% and coworkers of 82.59%) contribute to mitigating the potential negative effects of workload. This finding is supported by research by Vepriaria Permata Dewi & Majang Palupi (2024) in hospitals, which stated that workload did not significantly influence nurses' job satisfaction due to other factors such as *work engagement* and organizational support. Another study by Rokhmah et al. (2024) at PT. Sinergi Gula Nusantara actually found a positive effect of workload on job satisfaction, which was explained by a competitive work culture. However, this study did not find a positive or negative effect. In the context of JD-R theory, this is understandable because *job demands* do not automatically become *hindrance demands* that undermine well-being; they can become *challenge demands* that actually motivate if supported by sufficient resources (Bakker & Demerouti, 2014). At UP2B NTB, fairly good competence (score 77.33%) and high social support may have transformed workload into a positive challenge.

4) The Influence of Competence on Job Satisfaction

Statistical results: Path coefficient = 0.784; standard deviation = 0.247; t-statistic = 3.170 (> 1.96); p-value = 0.001 (< 0.05). Hypothesis H4 is accepted (highly significant positive effect). Detailed discussion: Competence is the variable with the largest influence on job satisfaction in this model (coefficient 0.784, *effect size* $f^2 = 0.478$, large category). This means that an increase in competence will be followed by a substantial increase in job satisfaction. This finding is statistically very strong (p-value 0.001) and stable (the *bootstrapping sample mean value* of 0.807 is close to the original sample). Why does competence have such a strong influence on job satisfaction? First, competent employees feel in control of their work. A sense of *control* is a key determinant of job satisfaction according to *Self-Determination Theory* (Deci & Ryan, 2000). In a technical environment like UP2B NTB, inability to operate a SCADA system or misreading data can lead to catastrophic operational failures. Conversely, employees who master equipment and procedures feel secure, confident, and satisfied. Second, competence opens up opportunities for recognition and rewards. Skilled employees tend to receive appreciation from superiors (good supervision) and coworkers, which enhances satisfaction. Third, competence enables employees to complete tasks on time and with high quality, reducing frustration and stress.

Descriptive results show that the ability dimension *received* the highest perception score (80.74% for the items "I am able to communicate well" and "I am able to work in a team"). This aligns with statistical findings that interpersonal and technical competencies jointly increase satisfaction. Previous research by Mantrawan et al. (2024) at PT PLN UPT Bali also reported that competency had a significant positive effect on employee job satisfaction. Jayanti & Heryanda (2025) at the Regional Tax and Retribution Service Unit (UPTD) of Buleleng Regency found a similar finding: competency had a positive impact on job satisfaction of non-ASN employees. Isuwari & Yudiaatmaja (2025) at the Buleleng Regency Cultural Office also confirmed that higher competency, higher job satisfaction. Therefore, the management of UP2B NTB must continue to encourage competency certification in relevant fields (currently only 22%) and provide ongoing training through the *Catalyst application* or technical training.

5) The Influence of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance

Statistical results: Path coefficient = 0.355; standard deviation = 0.122; t-statistic = 2.919 (> 1.96); p-value = 0.004 (< 0.05). Hypothesis H5 is accepted (significant positive effect). Detailed discussion: Job satisfaction has a positive and significant influence on employee performance, with a coefficient of 0.355 (medium effect). Although not as significant as the influence of competence (0.472), job satisfaction remains an important factor that cannot be ignored. This finding strengthens the classic theory of the satisfaction-performance relationship known as *the happy-productive worker thesis* (Wright & Cropanzano, 2000). Employees who feel satisfied with their work (happy, proud, motivated) will put in extra effort, be more creative in problem solving, and be more committed to organizational goals. In the context of the NTB UP2B, the highest job satisfaction indicators were supervision (82.22%) and coworkers (82.59%). This suggests that harmonious interpersonal relationships and superior support are key sources of satisfaction. When employees feel well-supervised (not spied on) and nurtured, and have solid coworkers, they tend to be more engaged and motivated. Conversely, the compensation indicator (72.22%) was relatively lower, but still within the high category. While salaries and benefits at state-owned enterprises are generally competitive, employees may expect increased performance incentives.

These findings align with numerous studies. Nurlaela & Trianasari (2021) at the Karangasem Regency Social Service reported that job satisfaction significantly impacts employee performance. Kusuma & Suarmanayasa (2024) at

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the Seririt Sub-district Office also found the same result. Santihari et al. (2025) at the Siloam Group Bali added that job satisfaction is an important mediator in the influence of the work environment and workload on performance. However, this study differs from Fauziek & Yanuar (2021) and Widya Nastiti (2022), which found no significant effect. This difference is likely due to job characteristics: in the technical and high-risk UP2B NTB, job satisfaction is more important because it influences employee vigilance and accuracy. Therefore, management needs to maintain job satisfaction through strengthening supervision, fostering coworker relationships, and improving compensation and promotion systems.

6) The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction in the Relationship between Workload and Performance

Statistical results: Indirect effect = 0.027; t-statistic = 0.257 (< 1.96); p-value = 0.797 (> 0.05). VAF value = 16.48% ($< 20\%$). Hypothesis H6 is rejected (no mediation effect). Job satisfaction does not mediate the relationship between workload and employee performance. The VAF value of 16.48% is below the 20% threshold, which Hair et al. (2017) categorizes as "no mediating effect." In other words, workload does not affect performance through the job satisfaction pathway; if there is an effect, it is direct (which is also insignificant, as in H1). The substantive interpretation of these findings is compelling. It reflects the reality of the work culture at the NTB UP2B, which is based on professionalism and systemic responsibility. Employee performance does not fluctuate according to the ebb and flow of satisfaction caused by workload. Instead, performance is a professional obligation that stands on its own foundation. Employees work hard not because the workload is light or heavy, but because they understand the impact of each task they undertake on electricity reliability in NTB. In an electricity system that supports the lives of millions of citizens, there is no room for conditional performance ("I will work well only if I am satisfied"). This depicts employees who have transcended the stage of working for satisfaction and entered the stage of working for the calling and meaning of their work.

This finding is supported by research by Hendrasti et al. (2022) at PT. X, Padang City, which also reported that job satisfaction was unable to mediate the relationship between workload and performance. Wulandari & Sukoco (2024) at the Surabaya Health Office added that the relationship between workload and performance does not depend on the level of job satisfaction, because employees have good time and stress management skills so that performance remains stable. From an attribution theory perspective, UP2B NTB employees may attribute their performance to internal factors (competence, responsibility) rather than external factors (workload, satisfaction). This strengthens the argument that organizations with a strong work culture can "break" the chain of negative influences of workload on well-being and performance.

7) The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction in the Relationship between Competence and Performance

Statistical results: Indirect effect = 0.278; t-statistic = 2.397 (> 1.96); p-value = 0.017 (< 0.05). VAF value = 37.07% (20%–80%). Hypothesis H7 is accepted (significant partial mediation). Job satisfaction is proven to partially mediate the relationship between competence and employee performance. The VAF value of 37.07% indicates that approximately 37% of the total influence of competence on performance is channeled through increasing job satisfaction, while the remainder (63%) is a direct influence. This means that competence has two channels of influence: (1) directly increasing performance, and (2) indirectly by first increasing job satisfaction, which then increases performance.

These findings enrich our understanding of the mechanisms of the competence-performance relationship. Competence functions not only as a technical capability that mechanically produces output (the direct path), but also as a psychological resource that enhances employee well-being. Competent employees feel valued, confident, and satisfied; these positive feelings then motivate them to work harder and smarter. In other words, competence "makes" employees happy, and that happiness "makes" them productive. This is a clear illustration of *job resources* in the JD-R theory, which operate through motivational pathways (Bakker & Demerouti, 2014). In the context of the NTB UP2B, this partial mediation has important practical implications. Management cannot simply improve competency through technical training; they must also maintain job satisfaction to optimize the effect of competency on performance. For example, after employees complete certification, they need to be given recognition, promotion opportunities, or more challenging assignments (job enrichment) to maintain satisfaction. Conversely, if competency is high but satisfaction is low (for

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example, due to unfair superiors or unsupportive coworkers), the positive impact of competency on performance may be diminished.

This finding aligns with Pratama & Rini's (2025) research on production employees at PT. Aerofood Indonesia, which stated that job satisfaction significantly mediated the effect of competence on performance. Khatimah et al. (2020) at PT. Sermani Steel Makassar also reported that job satisfaction mediated the relationship between competence and performance. However, this contrasts with Masruroh et al. (2023) who found that motivation (not satisfaction) did not mediate the relationship between competence and performance. This difference underscores the importance of selecting the right mediating variable; in this study, job satisfaction proved more relevant than motivation (which was not tested). Thus, the HR development strategy at UP2B NTB must simultaneously integrate competence improvement and job satisfaction creation.

Overall, of the seven hypotheses tested, four were accepted (H2, H4, H5, H7) and three were rejected (H1, H3, H6). The most prominent finding was the dominance of competence as the primary predictor of performance and job satisfaction, and the absence of any direct or indirect influence of workload. This provides empirical support for *Job Demands-Resources Theory* in the context of technical organizations: when *job resources* (competence, social support) are high, *job demands* (workload) no longer have a negative impact. Furthermore, the finding of partial mediation of job satisfaction on the competence-performance relationship opens up opportunities for further theoretical development of *the motivational pathway* in JD-R. This study shows that SEM-PLS is suitable for small samples (54 respondents) with complex models. A GoF value of 0.770 indicates that the proposed model has an excellent fit to the data, thus making the hypothesis testing results reliable.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of previous research and discussions, the following conclusions can be drawn.

1. Workload does not have a significant effect on employee performance.

These findings confirm that work is *real-time*, structured, and standardized through clear SOPs and job descriptions, so that variations in workload are perceived as a normal part of job demands that are understood and anticipated by employees.

2. Competence has a positive and significant influence on employee performance.

This finding confirms that the high technical demands in regulating the electrical system load require employees to have mastery of SCADA, transmission network management, and rapid decision-making capabilities, so that competency development through training, certification, and mentoring is an important prerequisite for continuous performance improvement.

3. Workload does not have a significant effect on job satisfaction.

These findings confirm that high or low workloads do not directly determine their level of satisfaction at PT PLN UP2B NTB. Employees in operational areas, such as those in facilities operations and load management, are accustomed to high workloads, which are often interpreted as a sign of the organization's trust in their capabilities. Therefore, these workloads are not always perceived as a source of dissatisfaction.

4. Competence has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.

These findings confirm that competence has a positive and significant impact on job satisfaction, particularly in technical and complex work environments such as electrical system load control. Therefore, employees must possess competency in their field to gain confidence and manage their tasks, thus fostering job satisfaction.

5. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

These findings confirm that employees who are satisfied with their work tend to demonstrate better, more productive, and higher-quality performance. Meanwhile, declining job satisfaction can also be followed by declining performance. Therefore, in the context of operational work at PT PLN UP2B NTB, which demands reliability, accuracy, and speed in managing the electricity system, job satisfaction is a crucial factor in maintaining optimal performance.

6. Job satisfaction has not been shown to mediate the relationship between workload and employee performance.

This finding reflects a professional work culture at PT PLN UP2B NTB, where high performance is maintained not based on feelings of satisfaction with the workload, but rather on the basis of employees' understanding of the meaning and great responsibility of each task they carry out in maintaining the reliability of the electricity system in West Nusa Tenggara Province.

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7. Job satisfaction has been shown to partially mediate the relationship between employee competence and performance.

This finding confirms that employees who have competent competencies not only directly improve performance, but also through increased job satisfaction which in turn can encourage these employees to provide their best performance on an ongoing basis.

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